

Aza Triterpenes II⁺ : A-Aza Triterpenes of the Lactones of Methyl Oleanonate and Methyl Betulonate

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Schmidt reaction of methyl oleanonate(I), methyl betulonate(II) with PPA and Beckmann rearrangement of their oximes (IA & IIA) with PPA gave a complex mixture. Treatment of the oximes (IA & IIA) with conc. sulphuric acid-glacial acetic acid mixture gave the lactams (IIIB & IVB) and the seconitriles (IIIC and IVC). Beckmann rearrangement of the ketolactone oximes (IIIA & IVA) with POCl₃-pyridine gave lactams (IIIB & IVB) and seconitriles (IIIC & IVC). Schmidt reaction of ketolactones (III & IV) gave the lactams (IIIB & IVB).

WE had earlier reported¹ the Schmidt reaction of methyl oleanonate, methyl betulonate and lupenone and Beckmann rearrangement of their oximes. It had been reported in the literature² that PPA was a superior reagent in the Schmidt reaction and Beckmann rearrangement. PPA acts both as a solvent and a reagent.

In the present investigation, Schmidt reaction of methyl oleanonate(I), methyl betulonate(II) and Beckmann rearrangement of their oximes (IA & IIA) with PPA gave a dark brown semi solid. TLC examination of this product indicated it to be a complex mixture, the constituents of which could not be separated by the usual chromatographic techniques (column and preparative).

Under strong acidic conditions, the pentacyclic triterpene carboxylic acids and their methyl esters of olean group³ are known to lactonise and lupane group lactonise with expansion of ring E⁴. It is therefore expected even in the present case, since PPA being a strong acid besides Schmidt reaction and Beckmann rearrangement, lactonization also might have taken place leading to the formation of the normal, lactams (IB/IIB) and 3, 4 seconitriles

(IC/IIC), lactams of lactones (IIIB/IVB) and nitriles of the lactones (IIIC/IVC) besides other products which could not be isolated and identified.

Since sulphuric acid is also a strong acid, Beckmann rearrangement of the oximes (IA/IIA) were conducted with sulphuric acid-acetic acid mixture (1 : 1). The reaction yielded lactams of lactones (IIIB & IVB) [IR 1665 cm⁻¹ the seven membered lactam carbonyl : 1760 cm⁻¹ γ -lactone carbonyl : 3220 cm⁻¹ -NH and the 3, 4 seconitriles of the lactones (IIIC & IVC) IR 1760 cm⁻¹ γ -lactone carbonyl : 2220 cm⁻¹ -CN].

The lactone lactams (IIIB & IVB) and 3, 4 seconitriles of lactones (IIIC & IVC) were prepared by the Beckmann rearrangement POCl₃-pyridine 30-35% of the 3-keto oximes (IIIA & IVA) of the lactones (III & IV). The lactones(III & IV) were prepared by treatment of the corresponding 3-ketones (I & II) with glacial acetic acid-sulphuric acid mixture (1 : 1) [IR 1700 cm⁻¹ six membered carbonyl : 1760 cm⁻¹ lactone carbonyl].

Schmidt reaction of the ketolactones (III & IV) (NaN₃-benzene containing a few drops of conc. sulphuric acid) gave lactams (IIIB & IVB).

* Part of the work presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1977 at Jaipur.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in chloroform. All the compounds showed consistent elemental analysis.

Beckmann rearrangement of the Oximes (IA & IIA) with PPA :

A typical experiment is described.

A mixture of oxime (700 mg) and PPA (30 g) was heated with stirring at 120-130° for 30 mts. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, neutralised with 50% NaOH and extracted with ether (5 × 100 ml). Removal of the solvent after drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, yielded a dark brown semi-solid (500 mg). It did not separate into distinct spots on TLC with various solvent systems indicating complex nature of the product.

Schmidt reaction of the Ketones (I & II) with PPA :

A typical experiment is described.

NaN₃ (0.68 g) was added with slow stirring to a mixture of 1 g of the ketone and 50 g of PPA at 50-60°. The temperature was maintained for 10 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, made alkaline with 50% NaOH and extracted with ether (5 × 100 ml). Removal of the solvent after drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate gave a dark brown semi-solid similar to that obtained in Beckmann rearrangement.

Beckmann rearrangement of the Oximes (IIIA & IVA) :

A typical experiment is described.

The oxime (1 g) was dissolved in pyridine (30 ml freshly distilled over KOH) and POCl₃ (1 ml) was added drop by drop cooling the reaction mixture in ice. After the addition of POCl₃ the reaction mixture was kept at 30-35° for 4 hours; poured into ice-cold water, extracted with ether and the pyridine was removed by washing the ether extract with dilute hydrochloric acid. The residue obtained on removal of the solvent was adsorbed over alumina column and eluted with benzene and chloroform. Benzene eluate gave the 3, 4 seconitriles. The seconitriles (IIIC & IVC) crystallise from methanol and acetone as colourless needles, (yield 100 mg) chloroform eluate gave the lactam. The lactams (IIIB & IVB) crystallise from methanol or chloroform as colourless needles (yield 300 mg).

Action of Glacial acetic acid-conc. Sulphuric acid mixture on Oximes (IA & IIA) : Isolation of lactone lactams (IIIB & IVB) and 3, 4 seconitriles (IIIC & IVC) :

A typical experiment is described.

The oxime (2.5 g) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid-conc. sulphuric acid mixture (100 ml : 1 : 1) and kept at room temperature overnight. The reaction mixture on dilution with ice-cold water gave a colourless mass. This was adsorbed over alumina column and eluted with benzene and chloroform. Benzene eluate gave lactone lactams. The lactone lactams crystallise from methanol as colourless needles and the chloroform eluate gave 3, 4 seconitriles. The 3, 4 seconitriles crystallise from methanol as colourless needles, and had m.p.s (IIIC, 245° and IVC 242°).

Schmidt reaction of the Ketolactones (III & IV) :

NaN₃ (0.5 g) was added with slow agitation during the course of 1 hour to a solution of the ketone (1 g in 40 ml of benzene containing 4 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid) at 60-65°. The temperature was maintained for 10 hrs and the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, made alkaline with 5% NaOH and extracted with ether (5 × 100 ml). Removal of the solvent gave the lactam (650 mg). The lactams crystallise from acetone or methanol as colourless needles and had m.p.s (IIIB, above 280° and IVB, above 280°)

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